

Young Researchers Seminar 2023

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RAIL DELAYS AND TRAVELLERS' PERCEPTION OF BEING DELAYED

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SUMMARY

Impacts of various aspects of journey on satisfaction of public transport users have been well studied. However, due to the nature of delays and difficulties in matching satisfaction and operational data, the research in that area is limited. As argued by Monsuur et al. (2021), passengers are unlikely to remain satisfied with their journeys following delays of more than 30 minutes. In line with previous research (i.e. Mackie et al., 2001; Daly et al., 2014), travellers are not always able to perceive small changes in scheduled journey times. Therefore, intuition suggests that similarly travellers may fail to perceive smaller delays. Against this background, this work related data on passenger perception of delays from National Rail Passenger Survey in the United Kingdom and recorded performance to study passengers' ability to perceive delays. Perception of arrival delay is modelled as binary outcome to study the effects of journey time, journey quality and recorded delays at both departure and arrival on passengers' ability to perceive delays at arrival. The results suggest that commuters are the most sensitive travellers with respect to delays, typically being able to perceive arrival delays as small as 2 to 8.5 minutes, depending on journey time, quality and the length of departure delay. For business and leisure travellers, the respective thresholds are between 3 to 20 minutes. Furthermore, for a given length of arrival delay, the probability of perceiving it increases with length of delay at departure and decreases with journey time and for seated versus standing passengers. While this research fills the important gap in the literature, further research could incorporate the impacts of differences between recorded performance and delay perception on passenger satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Intuition suggests that rail performance affects levels of demand, but passengers are not always able to change their travel behaviour following late running, at least in the short-run (Batley, Dargay and Wardman, 2011). This means that while delays have a negative impact on the passengers, performance may not be immediately linked to demand. Several studies looked at the impact of different aspects of journey on travel satisfaction and suggested that performance, comfort and provision of information are of paramount importance for public transport users (e.g. Brons and Rietveld, 2009; de Oña and de Oña, 2014; Susilo and Cats, 2014; Monsuur et al., 2021). Previous research suggests that passengers delayed by over 30 minutes are very unlikely to remain satisfied with their journeys (Monsuur et al., 2021) and, as suggested by Transport Focus (2015), satisfaction levels tend to drop from the very first minute of late running.

While previous research provides us with some understanding of how passenger satisfaction changes with delays, little is known about how passengers perceive delays and the effects of delay perception on satisfaction. Nielsen (2000) and Rezapour and Ferraro (2021) indicated that passenger perception of delays has an impact on travel behaviour and public transport suppliers can learn how to improve their services by investigating these impacts. Some studies indicated that passengers are generally less likely to notice small journey time changes, implying that benefits of such improvements are limited (Mackie et al., 2003; Daly et al., 2014). Similar arguments can be applied to delays and, as suggested by Wardman and Batley (2022) and Rong et al. (2022), further research is needed to look at the differences between perceptions of delays and recorded performance. It can be thought that the perception of delay is an intermediate step linking the delay (supply-side disruption) with its impacts on satisfaction and demand (demand-side impact), since for delays to have an impact on travellers they clearly need to be perceived.

This study used data on rail passenger delay perception from National Rail Passenger Survey conducted by Transport Focus in the United Kingdom. Passenger responses were matched to the operational data using the Historic Service Performance database to allow comparison between the passengers' reports of delays and recorded performance. A binary response model is estimated where passengers' ability to perceive a delay is explained by delay length (at departure and arrival), controlling for journey time, journey quality, and journey type.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. The first section reviews the key literature covering human perception and passenger satisfaction. Subsequently, a summary of survey data and methodologies used in this study is provided with the main findings and conclusions being reported in the remaining sections.

1. REVIEW OF STUDIES ON PERCEPTION

Human perception plays an important role in behaviour and decision-making. As noted by Manski (2004), Shepperd et al. (2013) and Lupyan (2017), the knowledge and memory of survey respondents may be imperfect, leading to discrepancies between self-reports and actual values. There is an abundance of studies looking at human perception in different contexts, which differ with respect to how easy it is to observe and measure a stimulus.

Crime perception research (e.g. Vallejo Velazquez et al., 2020; Manning et al. 2022) offers some insights into the divergence between perception and reality, but unlike transport delays, the crime statistics are not directly experienced by those reporting safety concerns. On the other hand, pain perception (e.g. Margolis et al., 1986; Haefeli and Elferin, 2006; Cimpean and David, 2019) is conceptually closer to transport delays as pain is, indeed, experienced. However, pain levels are subjective, as significant heterogeneities in their reporting have been found across patients. This means that unlike delays, which have an objective measure (i.e. time), providing an objective measure of pain is not always easy. Similarly, while the probability of catching a virus can be calculated, the risk itself is not directly experienced as the outcome here is binary – either becoming ill or not (e.g. ; Lau et al., 2003; Lewis and Duch, 2021; Shelat et al., 2022). Walkability and accessibility, despite being transport-related concepts, are also difficult to be objectively quantified, i.e. there is no single measure that can capture them, since using distance as a proxy is argued to be an oversimplification (e.g. Pot et al., 2021; De Vos et al., 2023). In terms of measurability, a comparison of perceived and actual test performance (e.g. Ehrlinger et al., 2008; Papamitsiou and Economides, 2014) is probably most similar to delays. However, significant conceptual differences remain as the delay may need to cross some threshold for the passenger to be able to notice it and is conceptually more similar to pain perception, in the sense that the longer the delay, the larger the negative impact.

A large number of studies looked at the impact of various aspects of journey on public transport user satisfaction (e.g. Brons and Rietveld, 2009; De Vos et al., 2013; de Oña and de Oña, 2014). In most cases, it is difficult to validate perception or satisfaction with a quantifiable service quality measure, i.e. satisfaction with seat comfort may depend on the type of seat, but the type of seat is not objectively quantifiable. On the other hand, delays have an objective quantifiable measure - time. In this sense, validating perception can help understand the relationship between the objective delay (actual or recorded performance), subjective delay (perceived or reported performance), and journey satisfaction.

A large body of literature is devoted to valuation of time changes, both in terms of reducing scheduled journey lengths and increasing punctuality and reliability (e.g. Mackie et al., 2003; Preston et al., 2009; Batley and Ibáñez, 2012; Batley et al., 2019). As noted by Welch and Williams (1997), minor time savings often account for a large proportion of the benefits of

transport projects. However, as suggested by Daly et al. (2014), passengers are often not able to notice the smaller journey time reductions. As noted by Mackie et al. (2001), however, even if the passengers are not able to perceive these changes, it does not mean that these have no benefits. Mackie et al. (2001) noted that these are similar to the benefits from road safety investments where changes in accident probabilities are not directly observed or noticed by the road users, but still have economic benefits at the societal level. If passengers are less likely to notice the small journey time improvements, it is likely that the smaller delays may also fall behind their perceptual levels. Rong et al. (2022) and Wardman and Batley (2022) suggested that research is needed to study the perception of delays and the marginal impacts of delay on passenger satisfaction and, ultimately, demand.

Studies typically focus on the relationship between perceived delay and journey satisfaction. As journey satisfaction data typically comes from passenger surveys, the journey times and delays are rarely validated with operational data. As argued by Nathanail (2008) and Rong et al. (2022), combining perceived delays with recorded delays can improve understanding of the impacts of lateness on passenger satisfaction. A few studies where this is explored include Higgins et al. (2017) looking at the relationship between satisfaction and duration of car commute combined with respondents' perceptions of congestion levels in Canada. Carrel et al. (2016) matched transit passenger satisfaction data with smartphone location data from San Francisco Travel Quality Study to relate satisfaction to unreliability levels and estimated a 69-percentage-point decrease in the proportion of satisfied bus passengers following a 10-minute delay. Gao (2018) estimated the impacts of differences between expected and experienced in-vehicle time on the satisfaction of public transport users in Xi'an, suggesting that the gap between the two can better explain satisfaction levels than the absolute values.

As noted by Batley (2007), while scheduling journeys, passengers incorporate a schedule buffer around their preferred arrival time to increase the probability of arriving at the destination within the preferred time. As noted by GLA Economics (2005), employees in central London typically allow 22 minutes of extra time while commuting to work. Analysing National Rail Passenger Survey from the United Kingdom matched to operational data, Monsuur et al. (2021) argued that the probability of being satisfied with a train journey decreases sharply after 30 minutes of delay (or 10 to 20 if a passenger is standing in a crowded train). These findings highlight the importance of both travel time and comfort for passenger satisfaction. Similar conclusions were drawn for air travellers in a study by Wittmer and Laesser (2010), who found the acceptable level of delays to be 30 minutes. However, the comparisons between delay acceptability levels of air and rail travellers are difficult due to the different nature of these two modes of transport. Transport Focus' (2015) analysis of the NRPS survey revealed that commuters are generally both least satisfied with their journeys and most sensitive to delays. According to Transport Focus (2015), passenger satisfaction levels tend to start dropping from the very 1st minute of lateness, but for business and leisure travellers they decrease less rapidly until a tipping point (respectively 5 and 8 minutes of lateness) is reached. Transport Focus

(2015) also suggested that for each minute of lateness, passenger satisfaction decreases on average by 3 percentage points with some differences between journey purposes.

The literature reviewed highlights the importance of delays in determining passenger satisfaction. With rail delays being directly experienced by the travellers and having a quantifiable measure of time, it is believed that comparing perceived and recorded delay levels may increase understanding of the impacts of delays of varying lengths on passenger satisfaction.

2. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

2.1. NATIONAL RAIL PASSENGER SURVEY

The passenger satisfaction data used in this study comes from the National Rail Passenger Survey (NRPS), conducted by Transport Focus in the United Kingdom. The survey has been built into franchising agreements and provides a passenger-centric perspective on the rail performance (Campaign for Better Transport, 2015). For the current study 275,000 responses from 10 survey waves (between 2015 and 2020) were obtained from Transport Focus. Each survey wave consists of around 30,000 responses representing different types of journeys and passengers. The dataset was cleaned by filtering out the responses where some data was missing. Subsequently, over 90% of the responses were successfully matched with performance data using the Historic Service Performance (HSP) database based on the journey details provided by the passenger. As part of the survey, the respondents were asked if they experienced a delay as shown in Figure 1. In this case, delay perception is assumed equivalent to reports of delay experience.

Q13 Did you experience any delay either on this train or because the train you had planned to catch at Glasgow Central was cancelled?

No delay.....	<input type="checkbox"/> Go to Q16	16-20 minutes delay.....	<input type="checkbox"/> Go to Q14
Up to 5 minutes delay.....	<input type="checkbox"/> Go to Q14	21-30 minutes delay.....	<input type="checkbox"/> Go to Q14
6-10 minutes delay.....	<input type="checkbox"/> Go to Q14	31-60 minutes delay.....	<input type="checkbox"/> Go to Q14
11-15 minutes delay.....	<input type="checkbox"/> Go to Q14	Over 60 minutes delay.....	<input type="checkbox"/> Go to Q14

Figure 1: Performance perception question from NRPS (Transport Focus, 2020)

As shown in Table 1, almost 1 in 2 surveyed passengers arrived at their destination late, but only 1 in 5 actually reported being delayed. In around 6% of responses, a delay was reported by a passenger, but it was not matched by the records – these responses can likely be attributed to the cases where a passenger intended to catch a different train which was delayed or cancelled. In this case, it is not possible to trace the whole journey the passenger was intending to make. However, it is expected that travellers are able to perceive an experienced delay and this research aims to investigate how the ability to perceive delays changes with performance.

Table 1: Perceived and recorded delays

		Perceived/reported	
		Delay	No delay
Recorded	Delay	18.0%	30.8%
	No delay	5.8%	45.3%

Typically, respondents failed to report shorter delays - possibly due to shorter delays falling below their perceptual thresholds. An average delay length of 2.7 minutes was recorded for the whole NRPS sample. For the subset of journeys where a delay was recorded, an average delay of 3.6 minutes was recorded for passengers who were matched a delay but did not report it versus 9.0 minutes for passengers who also reported being delayed.

Figure 2 shows how the proportion of passengers reporting delays increases with worsening recorded performance. As lengthier delays are relatively rare, the number of responses represented in the sample decreases with increasing delays. To take this into account and remove possible data errors, the dataset is constrained to delays of up to 30 minutes. This is also based on the indication that after 30 minutes of delay, passengers are very unlikely to remain satisfied with their journey (Monsuur et al., 2021).

Figure 2: The proportion of passengers reporting delays for increasing levels of recorded arrival delay

2.2. VARIABLE CHOICE AND DEMAND SEGMENTATION

As delay perception may also be influenced by factors other than delay lengths, the responses were split into 6 journey purposes, i.e. business (London/non-London), commute (London/non-London) and leisure (full fare/reduced fare), following typical segmentation in rail economics studies in the UK (i.e. similar to Batley and Ibáñez, 2012). The initial analysis revealed that commuters (whose journeys are typically shorter and subjected to shorter delays), tend to be less satisfied with punctuality. With suggestions that departure and arrival delays have a differing impact on passenger satisfaction (Batley and Ibáñez, 2012), this research also aims to

investigate the impact they both have on delay perception. Following suggestion that journey quality affects journey satisfaction (i.e. Monsuur et al., 2021), it is investigated how quality affects delay perception. 10.4% of the surveyed passengers reported not being able to find a seat for the whole duration of the journey. While the question was missing from the first three waves of the survey used here, this still allows to control for the quality aspect for the majority of responses. Thus, this research aims to investigate the travellers' ability to perceive delays while examining the impact of journey times, recorded departure versus arrival delay, and having a seat (proxy for journey quality) on passengers' reports of delay perception.

2.3. MODELLING APPROACH

Passenger responses on delay perception from NRPS were matched to operational data using the HSP database. This allowed computing scheduled journey time and recorded delays (at departure and arrival) for each of the responses. To increase the understanding of the passengers' perception of delays, this work aims to investigate how the probability of reporting a delay changes with increasing delay lengths while also controlling for journey types, journey time and journey quality. As the passengers reported whether they faced a delay at the destination, the delay perception is modelled as binary outcome where:

$$Y = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if passenger reported late arrival} \\ 0 & \text{if passenger reported arriving on time} \end{cases}$$

and perception is defined as:

$$P(Y = 1) = F(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_i X_i)$$

where X_i is an explanatory variable i , and β_i is the corresponding parameter and

$$F = \frac{1}{(1 + e^{-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_i X_i)})}$$

The ability to perceive a delay is modelled as a binary outcome and the probabilities of reporting a delay are estimated for increasing delay lengths for different types of journeys while also allowing investigation of the impact of journey quality and length, and arrival versus departure delay on delay perception. For each of the estimated models, a delay length with 0.5 probability of reporting a delay is calculated to compare how the thresholds where passengers start being more likely to perceive a delay change with changes in other explanatory variables.

If F is the cumulative normal distribution, the binary response model is referred to as probit. If instead, it follows the logistic distribution, then the model is referred to as logit. Both distributions are symmetrical and the main difference is that the logistic distribution has longer tails (Horowitz and Savin, 2001). The binary outcome models are estimated using the logit

model function in Stata 17. The estimated model coefficients represent the rate of change in the log-odds as the estimated model has the following form:

$$\log\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \beta_o + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_i X_i$$

and

$$p = \frac{1}{(1 + e^{-(\beta_o + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_i X_i)})}$$

The estimates can be indicative of the direction of the relationship and size, but are relatively difficult to interpret. In addition to the estimated coefficients, estimated probabilities are showed graphically and the delay length thresholds for the probability of perceiving a delay of 0.5 are compared for the different types of models estimated, i.e.:

$$0.5 = \frac{1}{(1 + e^{-(\beta_o + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_i X_i)})}$$

Three models are considered where in the first model delay perception is modelled as a function of arrival delay while allowing for heterogeneity due to journey purpose:

$$\log\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \sum_{i=1}^{i=6} (JP_i \times \beta_{1,i} + JP_i \times \beta_{1,i} \times L_{A,i}^+)$$

where:

JP_i is a journey purpose dummy variable for each of the 6 journey purposes that takes the value of 1 when it matches the respondents' journey purpose or 0 otherwise

$L_{A,i}^+$ is the delay length at arrival which is defined as the difference between the actual and scheduled arrival for all cases where the difference is positive

The second model aims to investigate the marginal impact of arrival delay on perception differs across journey times, by introducing an interaction term between scheduled journey time and arrival delay to the model. Testing how the impacts vary with journey type is in line with typical rail economics research (i.e. Batley and Ibáñez, 2012).

$$\log\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \sum_{i=1}^{i=6} (JP_i \times \beta_{1,i} + JP_i \times \beta_{1,i} \times L_{A,i}^+ + JP_i \times \beta_{2,i} \times L_{A,i}^+ \times SJT_i)$$

where:

SJT_i is the scheduled journey time

The third model extends model 2 by investigating the impacts of arrival versus departure delay as well as journey quality on delay perception of different types of travellers. This is to represent the complementary nature of departure delay's impact on the perception of arrival delay by introducing an interaction between arrival and departure delay to the model. The arrival delay coefficients are also estimated separately based on seat availability, which is used as a proxy for journey quality (taking the value of 1 if the passenger reported having a seat or 0 otherwise). As the reports of seat availability were not available for all waves, the sample size in model 3 is smaller.

$$\log\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \sum_{i=1}^{i=6} (JP_i \times \beta_{1,i} + Seat_i \times JP_i \times \beta_{1,i} \times L_{A,i}^+ + Seat_i \times JP_i \times \beta_{2,i} \times L_{A,i}^+ \times SJT_i + JP_i \times \beta_{3,i} \times L_{A,i}^+ \times L_{D,i}^+)$$

where:

$Seat_i$ is a dummy variable taking the value of 1 if the passenger was seating or 0 otherwise

$L_{D,i}^+$ is the delay length at departure which is defined as the difference between the actual and scheduled departure for all cases where the difference is positive

3. MODELLING PASSENGERS' ABILITY TO NOTICE DELAYS

As noted by previous research, it is important to understand whether and how passengers' perception of delays differs from recorded performance. This piece of work used data on reported performance data from NRPS matched to operational data to investigate how the passengers' ability to notice delays changes with increasing levels of recorded delays.

In the base model (model 1), delay perception is explained by the length of arrival delay while also allowing for varying effects on the different types of journeys. The estimated model coefficients are presented in Table 2 under model 1. In line with expectations, the arrival delay coefficients are positive and statistically significant for all the categories of journey purposes. This suggests that the probability of reporting a delay increases with delay length. The estimated delay length thresholds at 0.5 probability cut-off ($p=0.5$) suggest that commuters become more likely to perceive a delay after arriving around 4-5 minutes late to their destinations whereas, for other types of passengers this delay threshold is between 8-11 minutes. This would suggest that commuters are more sensitive to smaller delays.

Model 2 extends model 1 by the addition of an interaction term between scheduled journey time and arrival delay to investigate the impact of journey time on delay perception. The estimated coefficients are presented in Table 2 under model 2. While the probability of perceiving a delay is suggested to increase with increasing delay length, it is also suggested to decrease with increasing journey time. Figure 3 below shows the predicted probability of perceiving a delay for all the journey purposes for increasing delays at the 10th and 90th percentile of scheduled journey length for a given journey purpose (to take into account the differing distribution of journey times). As the predicted probabilities show, for a longer journey, a longer delay is needed to achieve the same probability of delay perception. The difference between the delay length thresholds for journeys at the 10th and 90th percentile of journey time is smallest for commuters (1.7 minutes) and largest for leisure travellers on reduced fares (4.7 minutes). It can be seen that at the 10th percentile of scheduled journey time, the delay length thresholds show considerable variation while scheduled journey times are similar. The delay length threshold is the lowest for non-London commuters at 3.4 minutes for a journey time of 20 minutes compared to 9.6 minutes for business travellers to London, representing a difference of around 6 minutes. For the longer journeys, the change in the delay thresholds is driven by changes in scheduled journey times rather than journey purpose. On average, an additional minute of journey time increases the delay perception threshold (at $p=0.5$) by between 1.5 seconds for business travellers to 4.2 seconds for commuters.

Table 2: Logit estimates of delay perception for models 1, 2 and 3

	(1)	(2)	(3) - seat	(3) - no seat
Constant	-1.741*** (-46.65)	-1.784*** (-46.70)		-1.666*** (-34.68)
BL	0 (.)	0 (.)		0 (.)
BnL	0.215*** (3.72)	0.187** (3.15)		0.338*** (4.60)
CL	0.714*** (15.06)	0.730*** (15.07)		0.783*** (12.71)
CnL	0.822*** (15.62)	0.823*** (15.32)		0.966*** (13.91)
LF	-0.0637 (-1.25)	-0.0854 (-1.63)		0.00961 (0.14)
LR	-0.0148 (-0.34)	-0.0463 (-1.03)		0.0416 (0.75)
Arrival delay				
BL	0.153*** (32.11)	0.195*** (23.63)	0.120*** (9.94)	0.150** (2.76)
BnL	0.185*** (26.92)	0.259*** (24.51)	0.145*** (9.16)	0.192*** (4.99)
CL	0.187*** (33.28)	0.238*** (25.84)	0.115*** (7.61)	0.229*** (8.55)
CnL	0.225*** (28.11)	0.305*** (24.90)	0.189*** (8.83)	0.336*** (10.32)
LF	0.185*** (33.69)	0.241*** (31.07)	0.152*** (11.96)	0.290*** (9.84)
LR	0.171*** (55.70)	0.239*** (47.80)	0.144*** (19.86)	0.247*** (10.83)
Arrival delay x scheduled journey length				
BL		-0.000358*** (-6.50)	-0.0000924 (-1.22)	0.000512 (0.86)
BnL		-0.000726*** (-10.47)	-0.000489*** (-5.19)	-0.000738* (-2.33)
CL		-0.00122*** (-7.57)	-0.000152 (-0.61)	-0.0000537 (-0.07)
CnL		-0.00249*** (-9.59)	-0.00168*** (-4.80)	-0.00392*** (-4.37)
LF		-0.000697*** (-11.24)	-0.000482*** (-5.51)	-0.000933** (-3.15)
LR		-0.000541*** (-18.74)	-0.000298*** (-7.55)	-0.000727*** (-4.05)
Arrival delay x departure delay				
BL			0.0204*** (13.27)	
BnL			0.0153*** (9.62)	
CL			0.0119*** (8.64)	
CnL			0.00792*** (4.94)	
LF			0.0106*** (9.56)	
LR			0.0147*** (19.54)	
N	73050	72884		48793
Log-likelihood	-41265.2	-40772.8		-26973.4
Pseudo r ²	0.135	0.143		0.167
% correct	71.68%	72.44%		73.41%

BL/BnL: business London/non-London; CL/CnL: commute London/non-London; LF/LR: leisure full/reduced
t statistics in parentheses, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Figure 3: Estimated probabilities of perceiving a delay under Model 2

Model 3 extends model 2 (see Table 2) by estimating the coefficients separately for passengers who reported seating and standing on a train to determine the effect of journey quality on passengers' perception of delays. Additionally, an interaction between arrival and departure delay is added to represent the additional impact of the length of delay at the departure on the delay perception for a given length of arrival (destination) delay. Under model 3, the arrival delay coefficients are positive and significant for all journey purposes and in both seating and standing scenarios. However, model 3 suggests that the complementary effect of scheduled journey length on delay perception is insignificant for London travellers. The coefficients for the interaction of arrival and departure delay are significant and positive, meaning that for a given length of arrival delay, the probability of perceiving a delay increases with delay at departure.

The predicted probabilities are shown below in Figures 4-9 for each of the journey purposes under the scenarios where passengers did or did not have a seat, for the 10th and 90th percentile of journey times and the departure delay of respectively 0 and 15 minutes. Generally, the predicted arrival delay length thresholds are lowest for the shorter journeys with a large departure delay and in the case when the passenger was not seated. In this case, the estimated thresholds are between 2.0 minutes for non-London commuters to 3.9 minutes for leisure travellers on full fare. On the other hand, the estimated thresholds are largest for the longer journeys with no delay at the departure and when a passenger was able to find a seat, between 6.4 minutes for non-London commuters to 19.9 minutes for non-London business travellers. This would be indicative of the impact that both journey quality, journey time and delay at

departure have on the perception of arrival delay. A more detailed comparison by journey purpose is presented in Table 3 while journey purpose summaries are presented at the end of this section.

Table 3: Comparison between journey purposes

Journey purpose	Overall Range of the arrival delay thresholds where the probability of perceiving a delay = 0.5	Departure delay Reduction in arrival delay at the probability of perceiving a delay of 0.5 if a train is late by 15 vs 0 minutes at boarding (other things being equal)*
Business London	3.2-15.9 minutes	4-7 minutes (no seat), decreasing with journey time 10-12 minutes (seat), increasing with journey time
Business non-London	3.3-19.9 minutes	4-14 minutes (no seat), increasing with journey time 6-15 minutes (seat), increasing with journey time
Commute London	2.2-8.4 minutes	2 minutes (no seat), 5 minutes (seat)
Commute non-London	2.0-6.4 minutes	1-2 minutes (no seat), 2-3 minutes (seat)
Leisure Full	3.9-17.1 minutes	2-4 minutes (no seat), 6-11 minutes (seat); increasing with journey time
Leisure Reduced	3.7-17.8 minutes	3-9 minutes (no seat), 7-13 minutes (seat); increasing with journey time

*larger actual reduction for seated passengers is a result of larger estimated delay thresholds for the scenarios with no departure delay

Figure 4 and 5: Estimated probabilities (with 95% confidence intervals) of delay perception for Model 3 for business London (top) and non-London (bottom) under the 'seat' (left) and 'no seat' scenario (right)

Figure 6 and 7: Estimated probabilities (with 95% confidence intervals) of delay perception for Model 3 for commute London (top) and non-London (bottom) under the 'seat' (left) and 'no seat' scenario (right)

Figure 8 and 9: Estimated probabilities (with 95% confidence intervals) of delay perception for Model 3 for leisure full (top) and reduced (bottom) under the 'seat' (left) and 'no seat' scenario (right)

Business travellers

Business travellers' perception of arrival delay is typically largely impacted by the length of delay at the departure. As the effect is larger for seated passengers and increases with journey time, this suggests that journey comfort has a large and complementary effect on the delay perception. It is especially the case when business passengers depart on time and have a seat on a train.

Commuters

Commuters' perception of arrival delay is much less likely to be impacted by factors such as journey quality or length. Being the most sensitive passengers with respect to delays, other things being equal, their probability of perceiving a delay is typically larger than for the other passengers. The perception thresholds decrease with increasing length of delay at the departure. Having a seat has a significant and negative impact on the delay perception of London commuters. Non-London commuters' perception of delays is less affected by journey quality and departure delay.

Leisure travellers

Leisure travellers' perception of delays changes similarly to that of business travellers. Delay at departure also has a very large impact on the perception of arrival delay as the effect increases with journey time. In the case of leisure travellers, however, seat availability and journey length also have a significant effect on delay perception on their own, typically decreasing with length of delay at departure.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This study used the delay perception data from NRPS matched with an operational dataset to relate passengers' perception of delays to actual performance. Passengers' ability to perceive a delay is modelled as binary outcome and is explained by recorded performance at arrival and departure, while also controlling for journey purpose, scheduled journey length, and journey quality. As expected, the ability to notice a delay at destination is suggested to increase with length of recorded delay at arrival. Generally, for a given length of delay at arrival, the probability of delay perception is suggested to increase with the length of delay at departure, but decrease with scheduled journey time and is typically higher for standing passengers.

Comparing the different types of passengers, commuters tend to be more likely to notice a given length of delay, typically being able to perceive arrival delays as small as 2 to 8.5 minutes, depending on journey time, journey quality and the length of departure delay. For business and leisure travellers, the respective thresholds are between 3 to 20 minutes. For all the travellers the arrival delay perception thresholds decrease with increasing departure delay - if a train is late by 15 minutes at departure, typically only a 2-7 minute delay at arrival is needed to achieve a 0.5 probability of perceiving a delay, suggesting a very large impact of delay at departure on the perception of late arrival. Moreover, the departure delay not only has a complementary effect on the perception of arrival delay, but also affects how journey quality and length affect delay perception. At the same time, these impacts are typically largest for leisure travellers and smallest for commuters.

The results of this study can be summarised by highlighting two key findings. First of all, large differences in the ability to perceive delays were found between commuters and other travellers. These can be potentially contributed to the differences in safety buffers around arrival times that passengers include for commuting and non-commuting journeys (as discussed in Batley, 2007). Moreover, with commuting journeys being typically shorter, a shorter delay represents a larger percentage change in journey time for such journeys, highlighting the relevance of both actual and relative changes in journey times in studying the impacts of delays on passengers.

Secondly, the present study suggests the complementary effect of journey quality, journey time and delay at departure on the ability to perceive delay at arrival, especially for non-commuting passengers. To some extent, this may be a result of phenomena described above. However, as passengers are suggested to be more likely to notice a delay when they do not have a seat, this may be contributed to more productive use of travel time among seated passengers. This aspect might have become more important over the recent years as digital revolution influenced the ways in which passengers use their time on board (Wardman and Lyons, 2016). In case of delay at departure, its effect on the perception of arrival delay may be linked to the impacts of waiting for a delayed train at departure (on platform).

This research fills the important gap in the literature by improving the understanding of delay perception. While this research suggests that passengers' ability to notice small delays is often limited, future studies might want to incorporate delay perception into the studies looking at the impact of delays on passenger satisfaction. This would allow understanding the impacts of delay perception on satisfaction.

One important limitation of this study is the inability to represent the possible impact of on-board and at-station notifications or access to real time delay information on delay perception. It is believed that provision of information about late running may be key in determining passengers' perception of performance, but it is recognised that obtaining such data is difficult.

While this study used the demand segmentation based on journey purpose, geography or ticket type following typical demand segmentation, future studies might look at the impacts of personal characteristics such as age and gender on delay perception.

In terms of policy implications, the most important finding is that passengers are less sensitive to small delays that are often unperceived. At the same time, the differences in delay perception for different journeys highlights the importance for acknowledging the potential non-constant valuation of delays. The policymakers' and rail operators' objective should not be to target travellers' perception of delays. Rather, the major benefits of increased understanding of delay perception for policymakers would be in incorporating delay perception into research focusing on the impacts of lateness on passenger satisfaction and ultimately demand.

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